

“A Practical Framework for Teaching
Entrepreneurship Using Modern
Techniques.”

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Abstract.

Entrepreneurship education is one strategy for addressing the problem of unemployment among recent graduates and senior professionals. Also, it reveals the need for establishing new methods aimed to prepare them to the different economic challenges and to reduce the risk of failure. If a country wants to improve the amount of successful entrepreneurial intentions, it needs to expose entrepreneurs to modern and adapted techniques fostering the ability to find new business opportunities and venture creation process.

A practical framework for teaching entrepreneurship needs to take all different stages during company creation. The model developed is a step-by-step approach that consists of five different phases.

To confirm the validity of this framework we conducted some seminars to senior students and professional who went through all phases and presented a final canvas business model.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship education, business model, SME.

1. Introduction

Small and Medium size Entreprises, SME, contribute as an important economic force for many countries. SMEs are created by people who in many cases do not have a formal entrepreneurship education. In our modern economy business skills become an important part in employability. Pittaway & Cope (2007). Therefore, entrepreneurship education will help to everyone to foster the ability to seek and evaluate commercial opportunities and increase the likelihood to start a business (Liñán, 2008; Mwasalwiba, 2012; Souitaris et al., 2007). Additionally, if we want to improve a positive attitude toward entrepreneurship, and enhance abilities for dealing with current challenges and an uncertain future, we need to promote entrepreneurship education at all levels. (Li ,2011: Heinonen & Poikkijoki, 2006)

Dohse & Walter (2012) indicated that entrepreneurial education can focus first on teaching the concepts of entrepreneurship and then creating entrepreneurial practical skills. Henry, Hill and Leitch, 2005 confirmed that for entrepreneurial development programmers to be effective, real work situations need to be taught in order to students to implement what they have learnt

As in many other countries, Nicaragua has started different teaching approaches to entrepreneurship education because it has been identified an apparent economic benefit, a way to encourage entrepreneurs and increase levels of economy activity. (O'Connor, 2013).

This paper details our experience in using a framework for teaching entrepreneurship using modern techniques. To confirm the validity of this framework we conducted some seminars to senior students and professional who went through all phases and presented a final canvas business model.

2.Literature Review.

2.1 Entrepreneurship Education

As published by World Bank in 2004, Entrepreneurship Education and Training (EET) represents any kind of education or training which the aim of providing entrepreneurial mindsets and skills to enhance participation in entrepreneurial activities. (Valerio, Parton, Robb, 2014).

Most of the higher education centers have offered a mix of entrepreneurship programs (Zamberi Ahmad, 2013). Entrepreneurship education has many advantages, like promoting business start-ups (Bécharde and Grégoire, 2005; Holmgren et al., 2004)

Any innovative approach to entrepreneurship education is considered a viable way for economic development. (Henry et al., 2003)

The objective of this article is to explore the entrepreneurial-directed approach to entrepreneurship education. The learning objectives of the framework are focused on improving understanding and enhancing skill of entrepreneurship among the students.

3. Proposed Framework

Two components are key to transfer entrepreneurship knowledge to students in an active learning approach; one is a spirited and experienced educator and other is the quality of the educational institution (Keat and Ahmad, 2012).

The documented implementation was conducted on five different phases focusing on transferring student awareness of entrepreneurship and practical experience of business.

Figure 1. Framework for Teaching Entrepreneurship

4.Results and discussion

To achieve the objective of this research, firstly was a survey of the literature on the entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship awareness, sales techniques, business planning, Canvas business model, idea prototyping, and local legal issues for entrepreneurs.

Secondly, based on literature review, we developed the framework shown in figure 1.

Thirdly, to confirm the validity of this framework we conducted some seminars to senior students and professionals who went through all phases and presented a final canvas business model.

5.Conclusion.

The study achieved its main objective because the framework developed was used entirely to create awareness of the entrepreneurship opportunities, challenges and rewards, as well as to identify and develop a business idea by using canvas business model with the creation of a prototype for further business development.

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About the author

Eduardo Orozco, a 2001 Fulbright scholar, has a Master in Management of Technology and currently is a Professor and Researcher at the National Engineering University (UNI). He brings both industry and educational experience to his position at UNI, having worked on a variety of managerial positions and projects on international companies. His area of research interest lies in innovation, entrepreneurship, broadband, smart grid, digital transformation.